

SCHEMAS IN HAUSA PLURAL FORMATION:
Product-orientation and motivation vs.
source-orientation and generation*

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1. INTRODUCTION: SCHEMAS IN THE MENTAL LEXICON.**

Recent psycholinguistic studies in morphology (e.g. Bybee & Slobin 1982, Bybee & Moder 1983, Bybee 1987, Köpcke 1988) have suggested that a model of the mental representation of morphology should include schemas of morphological categories to explain various properties of morphological rules that the traditional IA (item- and-arrangement) and IP (item-and-process) models fail to account for. Both the IA and IP models are exclusively source-oriented (or input-oriented), i.e. the only way to relate two morphological rules to each other is by taking a stem and a representation of a grammatical morpheme and formulating rules for the combination of these elements that are based on the input. However, there is evidence that speakers do not rely solely on the properties of the input elements of a morphological "process" (or "arrangement"), but instead on properties that characterize the product of the combination as a whole, independently of the properties of the input. A set of such product-oriented (or output-oriented) properties of morphological forms of a particular category is called a schema. Thus, Bybee & Slobin 1982 claim that although the Past Tense forms of English irregular verbs are rote-learned and stored in the lexicon, they are organized into product-oriented classes according to the phonological shape of the Past Tense form. They adduce forms such as strike/struck, stick/stuck, sneak/snuck as examples of Past Tense forms that are similar despite differences in the base forms. Schemas are said to aid in the accessing of these forms in the lexicon, and it is further observed that classes of items covered by schemas are defined in sets of family resemblances, not by sets of strictly shared properties, so that won, stung, and dug can belong to the same class. This similarity of schema classes to natural categories is highlighted in Bybee & Moder 1983.

Bybee & Slobin use the notion of schema only for irregular Past Tense forms in English. Since the number of irregular verbs in English is not very high, and only a small number of them can be reasonably organized into schemas, one might think that schemas are a marginal phenomenon, "simply...one of many ways that lexical information may be organized for more efficient accessing." (Bybee & Slobin 1982:286). However, there are indications that schemas are more important than that. Sometimes morphological categories are not like Past-Tense or plural formation in English, with one highly regular and productive source-oriented rule and a few unproductive exceptions that have to be learned by rote. For example, in German plural formation (as discussed by Köpcke 1988) there is no single dominant rule, and the large majority of plurals must be assumed to be stored in the lexicon. Clearly in such a case the notion of schema becomes more important, and Köpcke applies this concept in his study of German plural formation.

In this paper I want to discuss plural formation in Hausa. I argue that the concept of (product-oriented) schemas is very important not only to attain psychological reality, but also for the mere description of plural forms. Hausa plural formation is similar to German plural formation in that there are quite a few competing patterns, none of which is clearly dominant. But it differs from German in that the usefulness of schemas is readily apparent, and the various schemas have quite salient phonological properties. Moreover, plurals can differ to a much higher degree from their corresponding singulars, so that much more irregular allomorphy (vowel changes, tone changes, reduplication, infixation, truncation) is required in a source-oriented view. In a product-oriented view, however, the large majority of plurals are completely regular in the sense that they are canonical instantiations of one of the plural schemas. Thus, plural formation in Hausa provides evidence that schemas can be of central importance in the morphology of a language.

Finally, it also provides evidence for the view that mental categories are organized prototypically rather than in terms of necessary and sufficient conditions (see, in particular, Lakoff 1987). The schemas that I propose are similar to prototype definitions in that they do not predict the

system, but they make sense of it, they motivate it. Lakoff 1987 argues that mental semantic categories can often be shown to be motivated even when unpredictable categorizations create the appearance of chaos. This paper shows that an analogous situation is possible in the inflectional morphology of a language, that is, in the "hard core" of the linguistic system.

After giving a brief overview of the problem plus a sketch of the proposed solution (2.1.), and providing some background information on Hausa phonology and morphology (2.2.), I deal with each of the schemas in detail in section 3. Section 4 contains brief discussions of some alternative analyses of Hausa plurals within Extended Word-and-Paradigm Theory (Tuller 1981), autosegmental phonology (Halle & Vergnaud 1980) and upside-down phonology (Leben 1976, 1977), and section 5 concludes the paper.

2.1. HAUSA PLURAL FORMATION: AN OVERVIEW.

Plural formation in Hausa has traditionally been regarded as very complex. Quite a few different suffixes, tone patterns and stem changes can be observed in plural forms and it is not easy to perceive any regularity. Thus, Abraham 1959:25 states:

"There are certain types of word whose plural follows a regular plan once the singular is known., but in all other cases the actual plural in use must be learned, as it is impossible to know which of the formations...will be chosen."

Since Hausa plural formation is as unrestricted as inflectional plurals in other languages (e.g., English), it would surprise proponents of an IA or IP model to find that the vast majority of nouns must have their plural listed in the lexicon, as is the case in English in a few instances (child - children, mouse - mice, etc.). Indeed, in a more recent article we find the opposite view (Tuller 1981:131):

"Most Hausa grammars and textbooks, even those that admit that their formation is systematic, advise students of Hausa to learn the plural of each noun while learning its singular. However, this is no reason to claim that this is the case for a Hausa person. That is, given a singular, it is largely possible to predict what plural type it will take, based solely on its phonological shape. Thus, I won't suggest that singulars and plurals are both listed in the lexicon or that singulars are marked [+ooCii plural type], etc."

This statement is certainly much too strong, but the situation is not as chaotic as Abraham describes it either. To give the reader an impression of the variety of phenomena, I repeat the description in Abraham's grammar (1959:26-73) with some abbreviations:

(I) Plural formed by adding a termination

-áa	árnée	árnáa	"pagan"
-ái	jáahilíi	jáahiláí	"ignorant"
-áayée	gúntúu	gúntáayée	"small piece"
-úu	máashii	máasúu	"spear"
-íi	hánkákáa	hánkákíi	"crow"
-kíi	gónáa	gónákíi	"farm"
-únáa	jáakíi	jáakúnáa	"donkey"
-úwáa	hánnúu	hánnúwáa	"hand, arm"

(II) Plural formed by breaking up the root

(a) End of singular is lengthened by one syllable, VCV (the C being the same as the end-C of the singular))

(i)	-óoCíi	hányáa	hányóoyíi	"road"
(ii)	-áaC'VV	wúríi	wúraarée	"place"

(b) Middle of singular receives a new syllable formed from some of the original sounds of the singular

mágánáa	mágángáúu	"speech, affair"
gúntúu	gúntáttákíi	"small piece"
ákwáatii	ákwáatúttúkáa	"box"

- (c) Middle vowels are changed (and often consonant is doubled)

háráfíi	hárúf(f)áa	"letter"
k'wáryáa	k'òòrée	"gourd"

(III) Irregular plurals

míjii	mázáa	"male, husband"
b'áunáa	b'ákwáanéé	"bushcow"
lúudáyíi	lúuwáadúu	"spoon made of gourd"
gèezáa	gíràazáa	"fringe"

Abraham makes no attempt to bring any order into this chaos. Tuller 1981:153-55 gives a list of nine formalized rules, but leaves a large part of the data unaccounted for. I will return to Tuller below (section 4.).

A step in the right direction is taken by Kraft & Kraft 1973. They arrange Hausa plurals in eleven classes. The most important criteria for these classes are the tone patterns and the shape of the last or the last two syllable(s) of the plural forms, not the relationship between the singular and the plural forms. This enables them to assign e.g. the plurals qúntáayéé (from I above) and wúraarée (from II*aii* above) to the same class (their class II), because they both have the ending -áaCée, although they are related to their respective singulars (qúntúu, wúrfi) in different ways. Kraft & Kraft intend their classification only for pedagogical purposes, and they demonstrate its usefulness only for a small number of nouns. It also contains a number of inconsistencies and redundancies. However, I claim that an analysis along these lines is also theoretically the best solution.

In general, plural formation in Hausa becomes much less irregular and complex if it is viewed not as a process adding material to a singular input form, as in the IA and IP models, but if plural forms are thought of as existing independently of their singulars and organized into a number of different product-oriented schemas. These schemas are defined by phonological properties, involving especially the vowels of the last two syllables and the tone pattern. The plurals are also related to their singulars, of course, especially by having the same

vowels in the first part of the word and the same consonants. The following examples should make this clear:

(1)(a) riigáa	ríigúnáa	"gown"
(b) záurée	záurúkáa	"porch"
(c) táfkli	táfúkáa	"pond"
(d) álkálámíi	álkálúmáa	"pen"

Singular and plural forms are related in various ways: (1a) seems to show suffixation of -únáa and a tone change in the first syllable, (1b) exhibits suffixation of -úkáa, (1c) displays infixation of ú and suffixation of -áa, and (1d) involves a tone change in the first syllable, replacement of the third vowel (á > ú) and suffixation of -áa. However, from a product-oriented perspective there is no irregularity at all. All of the above plurals are instantiations of the same schema that is characterized by high tones followed by a low tone in the last syllable and the vowels ú and áa in the last two syllables. The only thing that is remarkable about such forms is that the stem characteristics and the plural characteristics are not neatly segmentable. However, the markers of stem and grammatical category are just as distinct and salient to the speakers as in segmentable morphology, only a more subtle analytical tool is needed than the conventional segmenting scalpel. I propose that the notion schema is just such a tool and in the main part of the paper I discuss a large number of Hausa plurals, especially "irregular" ones, showing how almost all of them are quite regular instantiations of one of the schemas.

A plural schema thus roughly corresponds to a plural class of Kraft & Kraft 1973. I propose the following seven plural schemas. Each schema is identified by a Roman number and its most important formal characteristics, tone pattern and ending. (The numbers also correspond to Kraft & Kraft's, with some mismatches due to different schema assignments.)

(2) I:	H	-ùoCíi
II:	HL	-úCáa
III:	HLH	-áaCée
IV:	LH	-áí/-úu/-íi
V:	HLH	-áa/-úu
VI:	HLHH	-áCíi
VII:	H	-áa/-úu/-íi

Before presenting and discussing each of these schemas in detail, some general information about Hausa phonology and morphology has to be given.

2.2. SOME GENERAL PHONOLOGICAL AND MORPHOLOGICAL PROPERTIES OF HAUSA.

Hausa has a canonical five vowel system, with all vowels occurring both long and short (long vowels are indicated here by doubling, as in other linguistic works on Hausa, although Hausa spelling ignores the length distinction). Syllables are of the form CV(X), where X=C or V. In a VV sequence both vowels are usually the same, giving a long vowel; ai and au are the only admissible diphthongs. Where the second V in a VV sequence is a high vowel, this sequence may also be regarded as a combination of vowel + glide (i.e., ii=iy, uu=uw, ai=ay, au=aw).

There are two basic tones, H (high) and L (low) (indicated by an acute and a grave accent, respectively; again, Hausa spelling does not mark them). In many cases each syllable has its own lexically specified tone, but often the number of specified tones is smaller than the number of syllables. In such cases the specified tones are linked to syllables from right to left, and the leftmost tone spreads also to all the other syllables that are left over (cf. Newman 1986b for a good description). For example, seventh grade verbs all have the underlying tone pattern LH. If the verb has two syllables, this will surface simply as LH (3a), if it has three, as LLH (3b), if it has four, as LLLH (3c), and so on.

(3)(a)	dáfú	"be well cooked"
(b)	kárántú	"be well-read"
(c)	bábbábbákú	"be well roasted"

The reverse case also occurs: If there are more lexical tones than syllables, one syllable may bear two tones. But there are heavy restrictions: Only HL is distinguished on the surface (LH is realized as H), realized as a falling tone (F) (indicated by a circumflex accent), and falling tones occur only on a syllable with a branching rhyme (-VC or -VV). The following verbs both have the same tone pattern HLH, which is HLH in (4a) and FH in (4b).

(4)(a)	kárántá	"read"
(b)	mántá	"forget"

This is how the tone patterns given above for the seven schemas have to be interpreted: H means that all syllables are high, HLH means that all but the penultimate syllables are high, and so forth.

The most important segmental morphophonemic process is that dentals (t, d, z, s) often alternate with palatals (ç, ɲ, ɳ, sh) before front vowels.

(5)(a)	búusáa	"blow"	búushée	"blow out"
(b)	fitá	"go out"	fícée	"pass by"
(c)	gúdù	"run"	gújèe	"run away"

Similarly, w alternates with y before front vowels:

(d)	háw	"mount"	háyée	"mount"
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There are two genders, masculine and feminine, but the gender of a noun is irrelevant for its plural. Besides nouns, I will also consider adjectives (and participles), which have the same morphological properties as nouns (and even syntactically there are few differences, so that the existence of the word class of adjectives may be questioned).

It should be noted that a large number of Hausa nouns and adjectives, if not the majority, have a variety of plural forms, generally all with the same meaning. In some cases, a given plural may predominate in certain dialectal areas, but in general the alternate plural forms are recognizable by speakers of any Hausa dialect.

The examples that serve as illustrations in the following are all taken from the excellent dictionary Abraham 1962. It covers several dialects and contains more words and variant forms than any single speaker would be acquainted with. However, the dialects seem to differ little with respect to the overall patterns, so it does not really matter which dialects and which words are chosen. In most cases the number of examples could easily be multiplied.

3. THE SCHEMAS

3.1. THE SCHEMA II: HL-úCáa.

This schema is most frequently realized with an n- in the C slot. In this way we get the "suffix" -únáa, which is one of the most common ways to form plurals. It is the most frequent pattern for disyllabic LH nouns (6), and it is also quite common for disyllabic HL nouns (except when these end in -áa, in which case the more productive schema I (H-úoCíi) is used.

(6)(a) riigáa ríigúnáa "gown"
(b) kántíi kántúnáa "store"

(7)(a) d'áakíi d'áakúnáa "house"
(b) géemùu géemúnáa "beard"

Other equally suitable ways to fill the C slot are by using the consonant -k- (-úkáa) or by inserting no consonant at all, in which case the glide -w- appears, the default value of C in the environment of u. (-úwáa). There are no phonological properties that determine which of these three possibilities (n, k, $\emptyset$ > w) is chosen, and it does not really seem to matter, since all of them are instantiations of the schema H-úCáa.

(8)(a) zaurèe zaurúkáa "porch"
(b) k'wàayáa k'wàayúkàa "grain"

(9)(a) kùnnée kùnnúwáa "ear"
(b) hánnúu hánnúwáa "hand"

It seems that n and k are among the least marked consonants in Hausa. They occur also in many other grammatical morphemes and might therefore be called "grammatical consonants".

Another possibility is opened up in the case of trisyllabic (or quadrisyllabic) nouns. These can change their penultimate vowel to ú, their last vowel to -áa, and adjust their tone pattern to HL, thus perfectly conforming to the general pattern HL-úCáa (such plurals where the vowels of the plural schema are intertwined with singular consonants are sometimes called "broken" plurals).

(10)(a) árzikíi árzúkáa "prosperity"
(b) tákòobíi tákúbáa "sword"
(c) ráak'úmíi ráak'úmáa "camel"
(d) álkálámíi álkálúmáa "pen"

Note that under a source-oriented approach there is no way to collapse the rules deriving (6)-(9) and (10); cf. Tuller 1981:132-33, 136, who has to formulate three different rules, thus missing an obvious generalization.

Furthermore, and even worse for a source-oriented approach, even disyllabic nouns can have broken plurals, where an u is inserted between the last two consonants, cf. (11):

(11)(a) táfki táfúkáa "pond"
(b) gárgé gárúggáa (Sk.) "herd"
(c) áikíi áyyúkáa "act"

These four subtypes are the core cases of schema II, and they alone would suffice to make a

case for a product--oriented approach. However, there are certain minor types that further confirm this view.

First, consider reduplication. Reduplication is an important property that figures in almost all plural schemas, and it can be manifested in several ways. The simplest is gemination of a consonant. The last consonant before the -úCaa ending is regularly geminated in the case of light roots (i.e., CVC-), as in (12)-(13) (cf. also (11c)).

- (12)(a) gáb'aa gáb'b'únàa "joint, limb"
 (b) gwádo gwáddúnàa "white cloth"
- (13)(a) zánèe zánnúwàa "cloth"

Further, the C of -úCaa may be geminated, especially if it is a root consonant (and cf. also (11b)).

- (14)(a) fángálíi fángúllàa "space at entrance"

This is particularly frequent in the Katsina dialect:

- (10)'(b) tákòobí tákúbbàa(Kt) "sword"
 (c) táadálíi táadúllàa(Kt) "bag of raw cotton"
- (15) (a) túubàlú túubúlàa(Kt), túubúllàa "brick"

A fuller version of reduplication involves the repetition of the -úC- syllable of the ending, together with the preceding consonant; the schema for such reduplicated plurals is HL-C1úC2-C1úC2-aa. Again this schema may be instantiated in different ways.

First, if the singular form contains a reduplication of the form -C1VC2C1VC2-, only vowels and tones have to be changed:

- (16)(a) takárkárfíi takúrkúráa "pack-ox"
 (b) taákúnkúmíi taákúnkúmàa "(sort of) turban"

Second, the last CVC element of the root may be reduplicated:

- (17)(a) shágálíi shágúlgúlàa "affair"
 (b) tséegúmíi tséegúngúmàa "scandal-mongering"

Third, most frequently, C1 is the last root consonant and C2 is one of the grammatical consonants n, k, w. In the case of n and w, this is straightforward:

- (18)(a) jákáa jákúnkúnàa "bag"
 (b) àbù àbúubúwàa "thing"
 (c) gâríi gârúurúwàa "town"

Things get more complicated with k, since obstruents are highly restricted in syllable-final position ("Klingenheben's Law", cf. Klingenheben 1927, Schuh 1972). Historically, velars changed to w by this rule, and this is still manifested in (19c-d). However, as the rule became unproductive and morphophonemicized, gemination of the following consonant became a frequent substitute. Often both are allowed.

- (19)(a) géemùu géemmúkàa "beard"
 (b) zàràfíi zàràfúffúkàa "opportunity"
 (c) gáashi gáasúusúkàa "hair"
 (d) yáajii yáazúuzúkàa "pungent condiment"

A minor type of reduplication is very similar, but has C1áC2-C1úC2-aa instead. Here are three cases with C2=n and C2=0/w:

- | | | | |
|----------|--------|-------------|---------|
| (20) (a) | tábòo | tábámbúnáa | "scar" |
| (b) | gídáa | gídáadúwáa | "house" |
| (c) | k'áfàa | k'áfáafúwáa | "foot" |

Another minor type of reduplication repeats the last root consonant to serve as the C of -úCáa (note that C is geminated in these cases, so there is a sort of double reduplication here).

- | | | | |
|---------|-------|--------------|---------------|
| (21)(a) | gáb'á | gáb'úb'b'áa | "joint, limb" |
| (b) | gárfi | gárráa (Kt.) | "town" |

Finally, there are several irregular cases that can be assigned to this schema because they share some of its characteristics. As it is assumed that schemas have an organization similar to that of other cognitive categories (cf., particularly, Bybee & Moder 1983), it is not surprising to find marginal, exceptional cases that do not share all properties of the prototype, just as there are some birds that cannot fly. Here are some of these ostriches and penguins:

- | | | | |
|---------|-----------|-------------------|----------------|
| (22)(a) | túbálfí | túbáláa(*túbúláa) | "brick" |
| (b) | gíndíi | gíndínáa | "base, bottom" |
| (c) | táakálmíi | táakálmáa | "sandal" |
| (d) | túfáa | túfáafíi | "garment" |

That (22a) belongs here is especially plausible since an alternative form is completely regular (=15a). (22b) also lacks an u in its ending, but it has an n which is characteristic for this schema, and everything else is OK. Still worse is (22c): Although the tone pattern and final vowel are correct, it has -VCCVV instead of -VCVV. Finally, in (22d) the tone pattern is the only indication that it might belong here. Such extreme divergence from the prototype is very rare.

3.2. THE SCHEMA IV: LH-áí/-úu/-íi.

This schema is regularly and predictably used for participles of the form LHH--CiáCiCiée, where Ci is the last consonant of the verb root. The ending vowel here is -úu.

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|---------|--------------|-------------|----------------------------|
| (23)(a) | sáamámmeé | sáamámúu | "available,
obtainable" |
| (b) | ráfkánánneeé | ráfkánánnúu | "careless" |

Similarly, this is the regular plural for the derivational class of place and instrument nouns (cf. Tuller 1981:135). The ending here is -áí.

- | | | | |
|---------|-----------|-----------|----------------|
| (24)(a) | márináa | márinái | "dyeing place" |
| (b) | mábúud'íi | mábúud'ái | "key" |

It is also very frequent and productive with other polysyllabic nouns of various tone patterns. The most frequent ending is -áí, while -íi seems to be least frequent.

- | | | | |
|---------|-----------|-----------|------------------------------|
| (25)(a) | kárfátáa | kárfátái | "shoulder of meat" |
| (b) | gòorúbá | gòorúbái | "dum-palm" |
| (c) | fángálfí | fángálái | "entrance" |
| (d) | fáatòomáa | fáatòomái | "he who lodges
travelers" |
| (e) | ábùokíi | ábùokái | "friend" |
| (26)(b) | áwásá | gáwásúu | "gingerbread-
plum-tree" |
| (c) | gígínyá | gígínyúu | "deleb-palm" |
| (e) | gájéeráa | gájéerúu | "short" |
| (27)(b) | d'òoráwá | d'òoráyíi | "locustbean-tree" |
| (e) | bàréewáa | bàréeyíi | "gazelle" |
| (f) | táuráaròo | táuráaríi | "star" |

Apparently, only nouns in -a(a) and -ee take -úu (cf. Tuller 1981:136 for a corresponding source-oriented rule). It seems that this pattern is specialized for loanwords from Arabic (28) and Yoruba (29), while English loanwords tend to be assigned to schema I (H-úCfi).

- (28)(a) misáali misáalái "example"
 (b) àlkáalfi àlkáalái "judge"
- (29)(a) káatáakùo káatáakái "plank"

However, there are also a number of disyllabic nouns that belong to this schema. Since its ending contains only one syllable, such plurals would have only two syllables. It seems that this is somehow too short, that there is a preference for trisyllabic plural forms. Plurals of trisyllabic singulars conform to this preference naturally (cf. 23-29 above), but plurals of disyllables have to diverge somewhat from their singulars. There are several possibilities.

First, an -aa- can be inserted in the root. This reminds one of schemas III (HLH-aaCée) and V (HLH-aaCáa/-úu).

- (30)(a) gúnkii gùmáakái "fetish"
 (b) gwárzùo gwàràajíi "undaunted"
 (c) gùdáa gùdáajíi(+redup.) "lump"

This insertion also occurs with trisyllables (note that in (31c) the aa substitutes for a root vowel).

- (31)(a) fáifái fáyáafáyái "mat"
 (b) gúngúmèe gùmáagùmái "log"
 (c) gùzúmáa gùzáamái "old woman"

In the Sokoto dialect sometimes the first syllable is reduplicated.

- (31')(a) gáb'áa gággáb'úu "joint, limb"

Another very common way is to add a syllable between root and ending, most frequently -ann- or -ak-, with ending -fi.

- (32)(a) wátáa wátánnfi "moon"
 (b) fùrée fùrànnfi "blossom"
- (33)(a) gùonáa gòonákfi "farm"

These are the only types mentioned in Kraft & Kraft, but in fact the data are more varied, cf. (34).

- (34)(a) (-ánnái) shéehù shéehánnái "deep scholar"
 (b) (-áikúu) záazáa záazáikúu "pubic hair"
 (c) (-ákkái) gùonáa gòonákkái(Sk.) "farm"
 (d) (-òokái) tsùmmáa tsùmmòokái "rags"
 (e) (-ákái) gùorò gòoràrrákái "kolanut"
 (+gemination, +reduplication)
 (f) (-áakúu) dàarfiyáa dàaràaràakúu "laughter"
 (+reduplication, +truncation)

The three processes mentioned in parentheses in (34e--f), reduplication, gemination, and truncation, all occur independently. First, reduplication: Besides the -VC1-VC2- reduplication in (34e-f), there is the more usual -C1VC2--C1VC2- reduplication, especially with trisyllables (but cf. (35c), with -C1VC1-C1VC1- reduplication of a disyllable, and (35d) with yet another type of reduplication).

- (35)(a) màgánáa màgàngànúu "word"
 (b) líttáaffíi líttáttáafái* "book"
 (c) gùdáa gùddáaddájíi "lump"
 (d) shùu shùwáashùwái "shoe"

Second, gemination: This is especially common with disyllabic nouns. Although trisyllabic plurals seem to be clearly preferred (as evidenced by (30), (32-33)), disyllabic plurals are tolerated if they show another frequent feature of plurals, gemination. Accordingly we get (such forms seem to be especially common in the Sokoto and Katsina dialects):

- (36)(a) yábùò yábbáí "praising"
 (b) gwáníí gwánnáí (Sk.) "expert"
 (c) fánníí fánnáí "category"
 (d) gùòd'íiyáa gwád'd'ái (+truncation) "mare"

(36c) again demonstrates the product-orientation: Not the relationship between singular and plural forms matters (there is no change, as the singular is geminated already), but the shape of the plural form. However, there remain a few cases with disyllabic plurals that are not geminated because the singular vowel is long:

- (37)(a) zàabùò zàabíí (but Kt. zàbbíí) "guinea
 -fowl"
 (b) kàazáa kàajíí "hen"

One might speculate that these are tolerated because they have the vowel aa which is a cue for pluralhood elsewhere, both in this schema and in others (see above, (30-31), and below, 3.8.(D)).

Third, truncation: A number of nouns ending in -iiyaa/uuwaa (a kind of overt feminine gender marker) drop this ending before adding the schema ending -íí/-úú/-ái ((39a) has only one syllable left after truncation and so adds -ann-).

- (38)(a) kàràuníiyáa kàràunúú "mat made of
 palm leaves"
 (b) gidáuníiyáa (Sk.) gidáuníí "calabash"
 (c) zíináariiyáa zíináaríí,-úú,-ái "gold"
 (39)(a) ùngúuwáa ùngwánníí "quarter of town"

The examples in (38) show that the preference for trisyllabic plurals is so strong that the plural forms may actually be shorter than the singular forms. Of course, such forms are unexpected from a functional point of view (and they are rare in Hausa too), but they fit perfectly into the product-oriented schema approach.

3.3. THE SCHEMA V: HLH-áa.

This schema is not quite as salient, coherent and frequent as the two schemas that were just discussed, but essentially the same points can be made here too. As with the other plural schemas, the tone pattern, HLH, is the most important feature. The ending is -áa in most cases, but sometimes -úu and occasionally -ái. Again, there is one derivational class that uses this schema regularly: the adjectives derived from "abstract nouns of sensory quality". Such nouns are of the form C'VXC-íí, and adjectives derived from them reduplicate the initial consonant in the singular (C1áC1-C1'XC2-áa) and the final consonant in the plural (C1'VXC2-áaC2-áa).

- (40)(a) zàzzáafáa záfáafáa "hot"
 (cf. záfíí "heat")
 (b) sàssáib'áa sáib'áab'áa "unlucky"
 (cf. sáib'íí "ill-luck")

These forms illustrate two common features of this schema (which can be found in other plural schemas as well, of course), final reduplication and an -aa- in the penultimate syllable. With nouns of the singular form CVCC-VV, an -aa- is inserted in the plural to arrive at the desired form of three syllables (C'VCaaCáa):

- (41)(a) sírdíí síràadáa "saddle"
 (b) gáarkáa gáraakáa "fenced plot
 of cotton"
 (c) gáarkée gáraakáa "herd of cattle"
 (d) téekií táyáakáa "large hide-bag"
 (e) zúuciíyáa zúkaatáa "heart"

- (42) (a) gúrbii gúraabúu "hole,
indentation"
(b) dúutsée dúwáatsúu "stone"
(c) múrfùu múràafúu "triple"

(41b-c) illustrate another possible consequence of product-orientation: plural forms may be homophonous even though the singulars are distinct. (41f-g) exhibit irregularities of various kinds. To derive the plurals from the singulars, one would have to assume abstract underlying representations for the singulars. In other cases, the last consonant is reduplicated after the -àa- (43), or a consonant is inserted (44).

- (43) (a) k'áfàa k'áfàafúu "foot"
(b) tábò tábàbbáa(+gemination)(Kt.)
"scar"
(c) dúhúuwàa dúhwàhwáa/dúfàffáa
"wooded place"
(+gemination, +truncation)
- (44) (a) ídòo ídàanúu "eye"
(b) gúndàa gúndàaríi "young fruit"

Disyllabic plurals are also quite common in this schema, but they obey the same constraint as those in schema IV: their last consonant must be geminated. The tone pattern HLH is realized as a falling tone on the first syllable.

- (45) (a) gáagòo gággáa "pagan villagehead"
(b) géefèe gyàffáa' "edge"
(c) góoròo gwàrráa "kolanut"
(d) túdùu tùddáa "hill, high bank"
(e) gúbbii gùbbáa (Kt.) "molar tooth"

Parsons 1975:438-39 reconstructs earlier reduplicated forms with -àa- (*géefàafáa > gyàffáa)*. These reconstructions may be historically correct, but they are not necessary to show that these plurals

belong to schema V. It is possible to formulate the schema conditions in such a way that they fit here synchronically ("HLH, preferably trisyllabic and/or with gemination/reduplication").

A somewhat deviating subschema is represented by the following nouns. They share the HLH pattern and they have reduplication of their final consonant, but they end in -ái-, and the penultimate also contains -ái-.

- (46) (a) tsíkée tsínkàikái "pieces of
dry grass"
(b) wáakée wáakàikái "bean(s)"
(c) tsúuwèe tsúuwàiwái "testicle"

Finally, there are again some cups without handles and vases without handles:

- (47) (a) túrkèe tírikkáa(Sk.) "tethering-post"
(b) gúnkii gúmùkkáa,-ái(Kt.) "fetish"
(c) yáa yáyyúu "elder sibling"
(d) fárcèe fàràutáa "fingernail"
(e) lúudáyíi lúuwáadúu "(type of) gourd"
(f) hák'óoríi hák'óoráa "tooth"

3.4. THE SCHEMA III: HLH -àaCée.

This is one of the most frequent plural schemas, especially with HH singular nouns (cf. Tuller 1981 for a corresponding input-oriented rule). The C is instantiated either by a reduplication of the last root consonant (48), or by zero, which in this phonological environment appears as $\underline{\text{y}}$ (49).

- (48) (a) k'ásáa k'ásáashée "earth, soil"
(b) wúríi wúráarée "place"
(c) wáagáa wáagáagée "hide-pannier"

Note that the choice between these two possibilities

- (49) (a) kúuráa kúuráayée "hyena"
 (b) kármáa kármáayée "infantryman"
 (c) gwáníi gwánáayée "expert"
 (d) wóofíi wóofáayée "useless"

depends largely upon the root structure: If the root is of the form CVC, reduplication is chosen, if it is of the form CVVC or CVCC, zero is chosen (cf. Newman 1972). This would appear to be an input-oriented condition, and it has been much discussed in the theoretical literature (see Tuller 1981, Halle & Vergnaud 1980). I reject this view and discuss the matter below (section 4.2.). A further possibility is to form a broken plural by inserting -aa- between the second and third consonants (only for CVCC roots).

- (50) (a) bírníi bíráanée "capital city"
 (b) b'ánáa b'ákwáanée "dwarf buffalo"
 (c) kyáurée⁹ kyámáarée (*kyáuráayée) "door"

Again an input-oriented approach would have to state two unrelated rules. Note the slightly irregular singular forms (50b-c), paralleling those in (41d-e). Sometimes two different plurals occur (especially if the broken plural is irregular, cf. (50c)), but they are not really distinct, since they are both regular instantiations of the same plural schema. In a few cases, trisyllables use this schema, and we get singular-plural pairs paralleling those in (11):

- (51) (a) gúzúmáa gúzáamée "old woman"
 (b) túkúnyáa túkwaanée (+y-trunc.) "cooking pot"
 (c) táb'áryáa táb'áarée (+y-trunc.) "pestle"

To conclude, again some freak plurals:

- (52) (a) úwáa iyáayée "mother"
 (pl. "parents")
 (b) yáá yáyyée "elder sibling"
 (c) k'wáryáa k'óòrée "gourd"
 (d) mùtùm mùtáanée "man"
 (e) gwángwán gwángwáayée "tin can"

3.5. THE SCHEMA I: H -óoCíi.

This schema is apparently the most frequent, most regular and most productive one, especially with HL nouns ending in -aa (53), although other tone patterns (54) and final vowels occur (55). C is regularly instantiated as a reduplication of the last root consonant.

- (53) (a) búkkáa búkkóokíi "hut of grass"
 (b) náamàa náamóomíi "animal, meat"
- (54) (a) táasáa táasóoshíi "plate of crockery"
 (b) láifíi láifóofíi "crime, fault"
- (55) (a) tsáuníi tsáunóoníi "hill"
 (b) yáak'íi yáak'óok'íi "war"

It is also common with nouns of more than two syllables, regardless of the tone pattern:

- (56) (a) fénsír fénsíróoríi "pencil"
 (b) tafáarkíi tafáarkóokíi "road"
 (c) ríijliiyáa ríijliiyóoyíi "well"
 (d) támbáyíaa támbáyóoyíi "question"
- (57) (a) tátsúníiyáa tátsúníiyóoyíi "fable, riddle"
 (b) tsúmángliiyáa tsúmángliiyóoyíi "cane, switch"

But even in this highly regular schema there are some irregular cases:

- (58) (a) dúukiiyáa dúukóokíi "wealth"

More importantly, even here a few forms can be found that exemplify other possibilities of instantiating C. (59) illustrates insertion of a grammatical consonant, and (60) illustrates zero instantiation.

- (59) (a) tsúmmáa tsúmmóokíi (+ gemination) "rags"
(b) yáaróo yáaróokíi "boy"

- (60) (a) tiwádà táwádóoyíi (*táwádóodíi) "ink"

There are even a couple of broken plurals.

- (61) (a) zúuciiyáa'ó zúkóocíi (+truncation) "heart"
(b) tsírkiíyáa tsáróokíi(+truncation)(Kt.)
"bow-string"

Finally, as mentioned by Tuller (1981:142), there are some pluralia tantum that fit in this schema.

- (62) (a) táamóojíi "wrinkles"
(b) kámb'óoríi "shell"

It is clear, therefore, that although schemas I and III exhibit more regularity and productivity than the other schemas they share all the important features of schemas II and IV. Their greater regularity seems to be of recent origin. It would not be surprising if there were an ongoing drift toward more uniformity of plural formation in Hausa. The best illustration for my point would then be some older form of the language. However, the overall pattern is

still clearly visible in the modern language. Let us now turn to two minor schemas, VI and VII.

3.6. THE SCHEMA VI: HLHH-áCíi.

This schema is uniquely characterized by its tone pattern HLHH. These plurals have four syllables, almost always a final vowel -íi (although -úu occurs, cf. 66a, 67a), and a short á in the penultimate syllable. As with other schemas, the C can be instantiated by k (for n, see the subschema below). In the case of disyllabic nouns, another syllable has to be added to get a quadrisyllabic plural. This is done by inserting an a(á) and reduplicating the final consonant (63).

- (63) (a) gányée gányáayákíi "leaf"
(b) gúntúu gúntáttákíi (+gem.) "short"
(c) káayáa káayáayákíi (+gem.) "load"

With trisyllabic nouns no grammatical consonant is added and a quadrisyllabic plural is obtained by reduplication of the form -C1áC2-C1áC2-íi:

- (64) (a) gáddámáa gáddándámíi "dispute"
(b) sháawáràa sháawárwárfíi "advice"
(c) dábaaràa dábárbárfíi "plan"
(d) kúncíi kúmármácíi (disyllabic) "cheek"

(65a-b) show the same reduplication, but are somewhat irregular. (65a) adds (and reduplicates) the grammatical consonant n, and (65b) is disyllabic in the singular.

- (65) (a) tsákúuwàa tsákwákwáníi "gravel"
(b) k'áryáa k'áráiráyíi (Kt. disyll.) "lie"

If the sequence -C1C2- is not allowed for phonotactic reasons, and minor adjustments as in (64a) (-md- > -nd-) or (64c) (-báarb- > -bárb-) are

impossible, an r is substituted for C2 (cf. also (64d); this is another effect of Klingenheben's Law):

- (66) (a) dúutsée dúwárwátsúu (disyll.) "stone"
 (b) númfáashíi númfárfáshíi "breathing"

Another way of obtaining the required four syllables is by inserting an -ée- after the first syllable. This is a very special subschema, and it is apparently restricted to nouns of the form C1aRC2- (R= r or l). If it is applied to disyllables, the grammatical consonant n is used to instantiate the C of the ending (68).

- (67) (a) kárfátáa kárèéfátúu "shoulder of meat"
 (b) mármáráa márèemárfíi (Kt.) "laterite"
 (c) tárwád'áa táréewád'íi "African catfish"
 (68) (a) gárkáa gárèekáníi "fenced plot
 of cotton"
 (d) sálkáa sálèekáníi "water-bottle"
 (e) bàrgóo bárèegáníi "blanket"

3.7. THE SCHEMA VII: H-áa/-íi/-úu.

This schema is the most limited of all. However, it certainly has a non-marginal token frequency since it contains some very common nouns, cf.

- (69) (a) mácè máatáa "woman"
 (b) míjii mázáa "husband"
 (c) yáatsáa yáatsúu "finger"
 (d) báawáa báayíi "slave"
 (g) sáá sháanúu (+grammatical consonant)
 "ox"
 (h) 'yáa 'yáa'yáa(+total reduplication)
 "daughter"

These forms are anomalous in that they are disyllabic, but note that the root vowel is a in all of them, even where in the singular it is not (69b). The same observation was made above for forms (37a-b)

of schema IV. However, other forms show the familiar insertion of a vowel (-áa-):

- (70) (a) túrkée túráakúu "tethering-post"
 (b) gúrbii gúraabúu "indentation, hole"
 (c) túnkiyyáa túmáakíi "sheep"
 (f) dóokii dáwáakíi "horse"

Besides these forms, one might include here the plurals of the regular derivational class of ethnonyms (bá-X-ée, plural X-áa-wáa, where X is the place of origin) (see Newman 1984 for these), as shown in (71). Some other nouns denoting people also belong here (72).

- (71) (a) bàmárad'ée márád'áawáa "native of
 Mádárfíi"
 (b) báámérikée ámérikáawáa "American"
 (72) (a) ánnábli ánnábáawáa "prophet"
 (b) táalikíi táalíkáawáa "human being"

My treatment of the cases in (69) is perhaps the most controversial of my schema assignments. Traditionally these forms have been treated together with those in (37) as "opposite" or "polar" plurals. To quote from Kraft & Kraft 1973:298:

"Class VIII plurals may be termed "opposite" or "polar" plurals. If the singular ends in -aa the plural ends in -ii. If the singular ends in -ii or -e the plural ends in -aa. The tonal patterns are varied:

kázáa	káajíi	"chicken"
míjii	mázáa	"husband"
mácè	máatáa	"woman"

A similar statement can be found in Parsons 1975:438. He also includes trisyllabic plurals like

those in (27) (e.g., kùyangáa, pl. kùyangí "slave-girl") that are assigned to class IV (=my schema IV) by Kraft & Kraft 1973:286. Furthermore, he distinguishes a special sort of "polar" plurals: the "polar plus" type, with plurals ending in -uu and -ai. Most of these are assigned to i class IV in Kraft & Kraft and to schema IV here, but Parsons also cites forms such as yáatsáa, pl. yáatsúu "finger" that I assigned to schema VII. The chief motivation for this assignment is to preserve the generalization that the tone pattern is the most stable feature of the schemas that is never violated. Compare also Newman's (1986b:253) judgment:

"In Parsons [1975:438ff], examples such as jiminúu and yáatsúu are interpreted as manifestations of the same -uu plural marker. In my opinion, this approach seriously underestimates the importance of tone as an essential component of Hausa affixes.¹² If one focuses on tone, one comes up with what is probably a more accurate grouping of plural forms."

Parsons of course tried to account for the quality of the plural vowel, but it seems hopeless in general to predict this vowel in those schemas that allow several final vowels (esp. IV and VII), and there is also a lot of variation (e.g., kántángí = kántángúu = "water pot necks").¹³

3.8. SIMILARITIES ACROSS SCHEMAS.

To conclude the discussion of the individual schemas, I give a summary of the properties that all the plural schemas have in common. These are:

- (A) A strong preference for three syllables (except schema VI, which requires four syllables). If the singular is disyllabic (trisyllabic in the case of schema VI), the ways in which the plural differs from the singular are also comparable across schemas:
- (a) A vowel is inserted between the last two consonants, either the first characteristic vowel of the disyllabic ending, or aa if the ending is

- monosyllabic: I (61), II (11), III (50), IV (30), V (41), VI (63a), VII (70).
- (b) The last syllable is reduplicated: I (53-55), II (21), III (48), V (40, 43), VI (64).
- (B) In the four schemas that have a characteristic ending of two syllables (I, II, III, VI), the last consonant may be instantiated
- (a) by a grammatical consonant: n: II (6), III (?52d), VI (68); k: I (59), II (8), VI (64);
- (b) by zero, surfacing as w after u in schema II and as y before g and i in schemas I and III: I (60), II (9), III (49).
- (c) by the last consonant of the root: I (61), II (11), III (50), VI (67).
- (d) a reduplication of the last consonant of the root: I (53-55), II (21), III (48), VI (64).
- (C) A general preference for gemination: I (59), II (12-15), III (52b?), IV (32, 36), V (45), VI (63b-c).
- (D) A preference for an aa in the penultimate syllable. This is part of the definition of schemas III and VI, and aa-insertion is one of the devices of attaining a three-syllable plural form (cf. above). In schema IV, another strategy used toward the same goal is adding an a plus a grammatical consonant (na, ka). Furthermore, this tendency favoring an a(a) has been observed in more marginal cases like (36d), (37?), (45c-e), (69b) (cf. also the irregular forms (22a, c-d)).
- (E) For quadrisyllabic plurals, a preference for a -C1VC2-C1VC2-VV ending. C1 and C2 may both be consonants of the root (III (16, 17), IV (35), VI (64)) or C2 may be a grammatical consonant (III (18), VI (65)).

One might think of these properties as defining a sort of metaschema that comprises schemas I-VII and would license other schemas that happen not to occur. The metaschema is much less specific in that

it does not contain information about tone pattern and vowels (except for the tendency favoring a(a)).

The fact that all these properties are shared by most of the schemas is evidence for formulating them in this form, rather than, e.g., specifying reduplication as a source for C in schema I, n in schema II, etc. It is true that reduplication is much more frequent in schema I and an additional consonant is much more frequent in schema II, but treating these frequency differences as categorical means neglecting the common features of the schemas and obscuring their coherence.

3.9. PLURALS OUTSIDE THE SEVEN SCHEMAS.

The vast majority of nominal plurals in Hausa can be assigned to one of the seven schemas described above. However, there are three types of plurals that do not fit in any of the schemas, and they are mentioned here for the sake of completeness.

One plural type is characterized by total reduplication, with two subtypes (the first subtype is very frequent with verbal nouns).

- | | | | |
|----------|----------|--------------------|----------------|
| (73) (a) | jéefáa | jéefé-jéefée | "throwing" |
| (b) | yánkáa | yánké-yánkée | "cutting" |
| (c) | shágálíi | shágálcé-shágálcée | "extravagance" |
| (d) | misáalii | misálcé-misálcée | "example" |

Another type can easily be described as involving suffixation of -áa. Note that the tone pattern of these plurals is the same as in the corresponding singulars and does not fit any of the tone patterns of the plural schemas.

- | | | | |
|----------|-------------|------------------|-----------------|
| (74) (a) | mád'inkíi | mád'inkáa | "tailor" |
| | cf. d'inkáa | "make by sewing" | |
| (b) | máròowácíi | máròowátáa | "stingy person" |
| | cf. róowáa | "miserliness" | |

This type of plural is restricted to the productive derivational class of má- agent nouns.

Note that we have succeeded in eliminating the wastebasket category of irregular plurals that Abraham 1959 and Kraft & Kraft 1973 had to use. The concept of irregularity is replaced here by that of non-prototypicality. Most of the plurals cited as irregular are simply less prototypical plurals on this view, which does not prevent them from belonging to one of the schemas.

4. THE ANALYSIS OF TULLER 1981.

Tuller 1981 presents an analysis of Hausa plurals within the Extended Word-and-Paradigm (EWP) approach of Anderson 1977, 1981. In EWP it is assumed that derivational and inflectional morphology are completely separate. Inflectional morphology is part of the phonological component, whereas derivational morphology is handled by word formation rules in the lexicon. Rules of inflectional morphology look exactly like phonological rules, the only difference being that they must be able to refer to the morphosyntactic features of the form they apply to. Tuller formulates the following eleven rules that are apparently meant to describe regular inflectional plurals exhaustively (I have changed the formalism slightly to make it more readable).

A. Disyllabic singulars

HL singulars:

(75) (a) /'x C 'VV/ --> /'x C C áa/ (=T's 18)

[-lo]
[-hi]
1 2 3 1 2 2
e.g. yáaròo yárráa "boy"

(b) /'x C 'VV/ --> /'x C únáa/

[-lo]
[+hi]
1 2 3 1 2
e.g. k'áuyáe k'áuyúkáa "village"

(c) /'x C 'VV/ --> /'x C óo C íi/

[+lo]
1 2 3 1 2 2
e.g. mùotáa mùotúocíi "car"

LH singulars:

- (76) / 'x C 'VV/ --> / 'x C únàá / (=T's 19)
 1 2 3 1 2
 e.g. ríigáá ríigúnáá "gown"

HH singulars:

- (77) /C'V(V)C(C)'VV/ --> /C'VCáa(C)ée/ (=T's 20)
 1 2 3 4 12 3
 e.g. bírníí bíràanéé "capital"
 b'éeeráá b'éeeráayée "rat"
 dámùo dàmáamée "land monitor"

- (78) /má 'x C íi/ --> /má 'x C áa/ (=T's 21)
 1 2 3 4 1 2 3 4
 e.g. mád'inkíí mád'inkáá "tailor"

- (79) /bá x C VV/ --> / 'x C áawáa/ (=T's 22)
 1 2 3 4 2 3
 e.g., báháushée háusáawáa "Hausa person"

- (80) /má 'x C 'VV/ --> /má 'x C ái/ (=T's 23)
 1 2 3 4 1 2 3

- or / x C $\begin{Bmatrix} ii \\ uu \\ oo \end{Bmatrix}$ / --> / 'x C ái/
- 2 3 4 2 3
 e.g. mázáuníí mázáunáí "lodging place"
 ábùokíí ábùokáí "friend"

- (81) /x x C $\begin{Bmatrix} aa \\ ee \end{Bmatrix}$ / --> / 'x 'x C úu/ (=T's 24)
 1 2 3 4 1 2 3
 e.g. tákàrdáá tákàrdúú "paper"

- (82) / x C V C ii/ --> / 'x C ú C áa/ (=T's 25)
 1 2 3 4 5 1 2 4
 e.g. tákòobíí tákúbáá "sword"

- (83) / x C V / --> / 'x C óo C íi / (T's 26)
 [+lo]
 1 2 3 1 2 2
 e.g. támbáyáa támbáyùoyíí "question"

In light of the above discussion of the various schemas, the shortcomings of Tuller's rules are apparent.

It was noted above that her rules (75b), (76) and (82) fail to capture the unity of schema II. Similarly, schema I is split into two rules (75c, 83), as is schema IV (80, 81). Rules (78) and (79) present no problems, of course, because they deal with plurals in two of the few completely regular derivational patterns. However, when it comes to less regular cases, Tuller's rules fail completely. And since there are so many unpredictable plurals in Hausa, this is particularly damaging. Tuller does not even make an attempt at accounting for the different sorts of irregularities that were richly exemplified above. Her solution is to put them in the lexicon with lexical redundancy rules ("parsing rules") accompanying them. She formulates the following rule for plurals like those in (41)-(42).

- (84) /C V C C VV/ <--> /C 'V C áa C áa / (=T's 35)
 [-lo]
 1 2 3 4 5 1 2 3 4
 e.g. sírdíí síráadáa "saddle"

This way of treating such cases totally obscures the close relationship to the plurals formed by rule (75), because the rules are contained in different components of the grammar. Tuller's justification is that there are less than twenty plurals that belong to (84). But one might ask where the cutoff point is at which a rule becomes an inflectional rule. As Tuller herself explicitly says, "In this ... view, the line between predictability and irregularity is drawn more clearly..." (p.143). However, Hausa is patently a very bad example for this principle. Whereas in English the distinction between predictable and irregular plurals may be clear enough, this is certainly not the case in Hausa. On the contrary, the evidence of Hausa shows clearly that no sharp line can be drawn between completely regular and irregular processes.

In (75a-c), (80), (81), (83) and (84) Tuller tries to restrict the class of singulars that can undergo this rule by adding information about the final vowel. It is probably true that there are certain tendencies in this direction, but counterexamples are easily found and have been cited above, compare (55a-b) with Tuller's (75c), (12a)

with (75b), (25a,b,d), (31b-e) with (80), (56b) with (83). Similarly, the tone patterns of the input forms are not necessarily as Tuller states them. For counterexamples, compare (9b) with (75b/76), (54a-c) with (75c), (49d-e) with (77).

I do not want to deny that the tone pattern, final vowel or number of syllables may often be an important indication for how the plural is formed. All I want to say is that Tuller's claim of predictability is much too strong and that under a schema approach more generalizations can be captured.

4.2. AUTOSEGMENTAL PHONOLOGY.

Halle & Vergnaud 1980:89-92 discuss some of the facts of Hausa plural formation within the framework of autosegmental phonology (or, more specifically, nonconcatenative morphology, cf. McCarthy 1981, who also briefly mentions Hausa plurals). In this approach, the phonological representation is split into different autonomous tiers. For their treatment of Hausa plurals, Halle & Vergnaud distinguish the following three tiers (disregarding tone, which would be on a separate fourth tier): the stem melody tier, the affix melody tier and the syllabic skeleton. For instance, the plurals *b'áwráayée* (of *b'áwrée*) "fig- tree" and *bíráanée* (of *bírni*) "capital" are represented in the following way:

Clearly, the separation of the syllabic skeleton and the vowels of the affix melody is a useful idea, and we have made use of the same idea above by describing the characteristics of this schema as *-aaCée*. But Halle & Vergnaud make more specific proposals concerning the mechanisms by which the output forms are derived. For plurals like *dámáamée* (sg. *dámùo*) "land monitor", the effect of reduplication arises from the additional link between

the last consonant of the stem melody and the empty C slot of the suffix skeleton that is required by the general well-formedness condition:

In plurals like *bíráanée*, the effect of breaking up the root arises from the stipulation that the stem skeleton must end with a single C. By linking to the suffix C slot the final consonant of the stem melody can survive (see (85) above). In the case of plurals like *b'áwráayée*, two Cs are allowed at the end of the stem, so that the sequence *b'awr-* can remain intact. In addition, the empty C slot in the suffix will be linked to the last stem consonant in conformity with the well-formedness condition:

This would give the wrong output **b'áwráarée*, of course, and therefore a special rule is required which severs the link that was just established in the case of stems with branching melody segments (i.e., heavy stems). Now a default rule can apply that links any C slot that is not otherwise filled to a *y*. This analysis has a number of serious shortcomings. First, Halle & Vergnaud fail to explain why the special rule that severs the link in plurals like *b'áwráayée* (see (87)) should apply only to nouns with heavy stems. They cannot make the correct generalization because their approach is essentially item-and-process and does not naturally include output-oriented constraints. But again, a product-oriented condition gives the correct results for the above forms: There seems to be a strong preference for trisyllabic plurals to contain exactly four (C or

V) slots that are filled with an element characteristic of the stem. If the C slot of the ending were not filled by a copy of the last stem consonant in light stems like dámù, a plural form like *dámáayée would contain only three characteristic stem elements. On the other hand, if there were reduplication in heavy stems, too, a plural like *b'áwráarée would contain five characteristic elements. The other possibility that is open to heavy stem nouns is that exemplified by bíráané: The last consonant of the stem can fill the C slot of the ending, but there are still exactly four characteristic elements. This explanation also extends to plural schema II: Singulars with a light stem must have a geminated (12-13) or a reduplicated plural (18, 20). The fact that in that schema the additional strategy of gemination is used to achieve the desired output is a further argument in favor of a strongly product-oriented analysis.

Second, by treating reduplication in cases like (86) as an automatic consequence of a universal well-formedness condition they lose the possibility of making the obvious connection between plural semantics and reduplication (this is a universal connection, of course; see Moravcsik 1978).

Third, the relationship between this type of reduplication and other types of reduplication found in Hausa plurals is obscured. To see this, cf. Halle & Vergnaud's analysis of plurals like tsákwànkwání (65a above) "advices" and qáddándámí (64a) "disputes". The first would be derived by reduplicating the plural suffix melody and by linking the last stem consonant to an unfilled C slot.

However, the derivation of qáddándámí looks completely different: First the skeleton is extended by copying the last syllable of the stem. Concomitantly with the extension of the skeleton the stem melody is copied. Linking now proceeds from

right to left, and since in this case only a single melody element can be linked with a given slot, some stem melody segments remain unlinked and are therefore deleted by a general convention.

This account thus fails to capture the obvious similarities of the two cases, and to derive plurals like tárbewád'í (67c) "catfish", yet another radically different type of derivation would have to be posited. To conclude, autosegmental phonology does not seem to shed much new light on the problem of Hausa plural formation since it also is fundamentally source-oriented.

4.3. LEBEN'S PARSING ANALYSIS.

Leben 1976 and 1977 proposes a theoretical framework in which the surface forms are all listed in the lexicon and phonological rules have an interpretive function (called "upside-down" phonology in Leben & Robinson 1977). This allows him to relate irregular as well as regular plurals to their singulars. Leben's analysis is similar to mine in that he proposes to put all plurals in the lexicon, which makes a unified view of plurals possible, be they highly irregular or completely regular. He also gives a rule (Leben 1976:431) that captures the similarity between plurals like sárútsáa (sg. sártseé) "splinter", hánnúwáa (sg. hánnúu) "hand", and tákúbáa (sg. tákuobíi) "sword" and is even extendable to analogous cases in schema III. In these two respects his treatment is superior to Tuller's. However, his theory is only superficially product-oriented. It is the application of the rules that is reversed, starting from the surface form, but the rules themselves look very much like standard generative rules, like those of Tuller in 4.1. above. Let us look at a sample derivation that relates the plural máaqúnqúnáa to its singular máaqání "medicine". The morphological rule is

(90) [Q V] => ['Q-úwáa] (=L's 25)
 1 2 1 PL

First, the rule of w-epenthesis is undone in the morphological rule, giving an expected plural ['Q-ú- áa]. Next, the reduplication rule is undone in the lexical form máqúnqúnáa, giving máqúnáa. Third, the infixation rule is undone, giving máaq(V)n-ú-áa. This form matches the plural of the modified morphological rule, with Q = máaq(V)n-, and máaqàní matches the singular of that rule, with Q=máaqàn-. The two Qs are compatible and therefore máaqúnqúnáa can be related to the singular máaqàní. I think it is obvious that this solution leaves much to be desired (both the surface form and the rule template have to be modified before they can match, and the infixation rule is rather undesirable).

5. CONCLUSION.

The facts presented in Section 3 clearly indicate that any morphological theory that is exclusively source-oriented cannot satisfactorily account for plural formation in Hausa. Quite a few generalizations become storable only if a product-oriented view is adopted. Specifically, it was proposed that the notion of schema that was developed in psycholinguistic studies in morphology could be fruitfully employed for the description of the various plural patterns. Seven schemas were described and it was shown that practically all Hausa nominal plurals belong to one of them. In this view a much more regular view of Hausa plurals emerges, because although the correspondences between singular and plural forms are often irregular and unpredictable, the plural forms are overwhelmingly regular instantiations of one of the schemas.

The organization of the morphological class of plurals in Hausa is thus very similar to the way mental semantic classes are commonly structured. Lakoff 1987 shows that mental categories are not defined by necessary and sufficient conditions, but are rather organized prototypically. Non-central instances of the category are not irregular, but simply further away from the prototype. If one tries

to approach the category in terms of clear-cut definitions, one seems to be facing a chaotic situation (which Lakoff nicely illustrates with the example of Dyrbal noun classifiers). But, according to Lakoff, unpredictability does not mean chaos. Often principles do not predict or generate a system, but they nevertheless motivate it, or make sense of it. Such is the case with plurals in Hausa: the schemas that I have proposed do not predict the individual forms, but they motivate all of them. Lakoff 1987 makes his point mainly by discussing semantic mental categories. By providing a detailed example for a very similar case from the "hard core" of the linguistic system, nominal inflectional morphology, the present paper supports Lakoff's view and underlines its importance for linguistics.

One does not often see cases of such a strongly product-oriented morphological category in the literature. However, if such cases exist, this suggests that schemas of the type assumed here are not merely a minor mechanism of performance that may play a role in lexical accessing, but that they are an equally possible way of organizing morphological categories. This supports Bybee's (1987) proposal that there is no bifurcation between morphological rules and representations; rather, affixation of morphemes is viewed as a special case of more general principles of lexical organization.

ENDNOTES

* EDITORIAL NOTE: Due to unfortunate constraints of time and geography, the author was unable to proofread the version of the paper that appears in this volume. The BWPL Editorial Committee apologizes to both the author and the reader for any errors that may appear in this paper because of these limitations.

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1. Or manipulating a singular input form in a number of other ways. The need for such other mechanisms has been stressed by Anderson 1977, 1981, who therefore advocates an "Extended Word-and-Paradigm" model. The input-orientation is even stronger here, since there is no "item" that all the output forms have in common.

2. I systematically distinguish between ending and suffix. A suffix is a morpheme that is added to a stem by a morphological process in an input-oriented model, while an ending is the characteristic last part of a schema. Since nothing is said about the relationship to the singular form, the ending may be arrived at by adding something to the singular, by modifying the singular or even by reducing the singular.

3. ɛ, ɔ, and sh are [ʔ], [dʒ] and [ʃ], respectively in IPA; note that there is no contrast between voiced fricative and voiced affricate corresponding to the contrast ɛ/sh.

4. The Katsina and Sokoto dialects are marked by (Kt.) and (Sk.) in Abraham 1962 and here. The standard language (unmarked) is based on the Kano dialect.

5. This word of course has only two syllables, but as it ends in a consonant ("fáyfáy") it has the same number of syllables before the final vowel as trisyllables. Hausa treats consonant-final nouns as if they had an additional syllable with respect to other rules as well. The two sources for final consonants are loanwords (e.g., kwap "cup") and loss of vowels in certain environments (fáyfáy < *fáyfáyii).

6. Derived from lit-tàaf-tàaf-tái by regular phonological and morphophonemic rules.

7. The a here is due to a phonological rule that lowers mid vowels (e and o) to a in closed syllables (cf., e.g., mútaanée "men", but mútaanán "the men" with the "article" - n.)

8. See also Newman 1986a:119.

9. b'áunáa and kyáurée arose from *b'ák(w)náa and *kyámree, respectively, by Klingenberg's Law.

10. from *zúkciiyáa.

11. Cf. Parsons 1975:439: "...plurals of the now common and rapidly spreading pattern -CùoCíi are clearly of later origin..."

12. I think that Newman is wrong in linking the tone pattern directly to the accompanying affix rather than taking it as a separate independent property of a morphological category. This view forces him to assume a zero affix in imperatives to explain the uniform LH pattern (p. 256), clearly an undesirable conclusion.

13. If the tone pattern is the single most reliable feature of a given schema, one might consider collapsing schemas III and V (both are HLH) and schemas I and VII (both are H). Since schemas III and I are internally very homogeneous, I have chosen to give them independent status, mainly for reasons of exposition. But one might very well think of them as special cases of schemas V and VII respectively.

14. An additional morpholexical subrule is needed to derive plurals like these (Tuller 1981:141).

15. It is not at all unexpected to find that even though in general plural formation cannot be predicted, it is highly predictable with nouns that belong to a particular (open) derivational class. The same is true for German, cf. Köpcke 1988.

16. As we noted above, this is true only for certain environments. In other environments, especially after u, w is the default C.

17. Similarly, Halle & Vergnaud 1980 (following McCarthy) derive the Arabic second stem kattab from the consonantal melody ktb and the skeleton CaCCaC in the following way: First universal linking conventions apply, giving katbab, and then the link between the third C and the b is severed, allowing the t to link to it, which gives the correct result, kattab. This is not only very complicated and

counterintuitive, but it also makes impossible capturing the relationship between consonant gemination and the "intensive" meaning of the second stem.

18. Leben's reduplication rule takes a plural form $X-únáa$ as input, thus permitting to collapse plurals like $ǰákúnkúnáa$ (sg. $ǰákáa$) (13a) "bag" and $máaǰúnǰúnáa$ (sg. $máaǰánfi$) (cf. 12) "medicine". However, it is not clear how the similarity to plurals like $tákúrkúráa$ (sg. $tákárkárfi$) (11a) "pack-ox" could be captured.

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